

IJOBIY RUHIY HOLATNI IFODALOVCHI FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLARNI SEMANTIK TAHLILI

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Abstract: In communication, Phrases are very important in any languages. These phrases keep us alive, whether they are positive or not, so let's learn to speak about them in English and share our joys and sorrows with our loved ones and friends. In this article, positive hypothetical units were shown with vivid examples.

Key words: Mental state, positive, all the range, mind, language, out of side, out of mind

Abstract: Har qanday tilda iboralar juda muhim. Bu iboralar uning his-tuyg'ular va his-tuyg'ularni ijobiymi yoki yo'qmi, bizni tirik qiladi, shuning uchun keling, ular haqida ingliz tilida gapirishni o'rganaylik va quvonch va qayg'ularimizni yaqinlarimiz va do'stlarimiz bilan baham ko'raylik. Bu maqolada ijobiy farazologik birliklarni yorqin misollar bilan ko'rsatib berildi.

Idioma - odatda iboraga birlashtirilgan ko'chma, so'zma-so'z bo'lmagan ma'noni ifodalovchi ibora yoki ibora; lekin ayrim frazemalar frazemaning to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ma'nosini saqlab qolgan holda ko'chma iboraga aylanadi. Formulali til turkumiga kiruvchi idiomaning ko'chma ma'nosi to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ma'nosidan farq qiladi. Idiomalar barcha tillarda tez-tez uchraydi; Faqat ingliz tilida yigirma besh millionga yaqin idiomatik iboralar mavjud

Maqtov - bu boshqa birovga ular haqida aytgan yoqimli so'z. Siz birovning tashqi ko'rinishini (kiyimi, tabassumi, ko'zlari va boshqalar), uning ishini (yozuvi, san'ati va boshqalar) yoki hatto siz hayratga soladigan fazilatlarini maqtashingiz mumkin. Biror kishini berish sizni yaxshi his qiladi, shuningdek, iltifotlarni qabul qilish sizni yaxshi his qiladi.

Tuyg'ular va his-tuyg'ular ham ijobiy, ham salbiy bo'lishi mumkin. Biz har kuni u yoki bu tuyg'uni boshdan kechiramiz va ba'zida shunday quvonchli yoki hayajonli kunlar bo'ladiki, biz shunchaki ijobiy his-tuyg'ularga to'lamiz.

Garchi ijobiy iboralar barcha madaniyatlarda qo'llanilsa-da, ular uzbek va ingliz madaniyati uchun ayniqsa muhimdir. Ularning tez-tez ishlatilishiga bir nechta misollar:

Sport o'ynash. Uzbeklar va Amerikaliklar sportni yaxshi ko'radilar. Eng mashhur jamoaviy sport turlari - beysbol, futbol, basketbol, futbol va xokkey. Sport o'ynashda ijobiy iboralar muhim ahamiyatga ega. Murabbiylar va jamoadoshlar bir-birlariga dalda beruvchi so'zlar bilan yaxshiroq o'ynashga yordam berishlari mumkin

Ishlamoqda. Amerikaliklar mehnatkash odamlar guruhidir. CNN Money Amerika Qo'shma Shtatlarini dunyodagi eng mehnatkash davlatlar ro'yxatida 7-o'ringa qo'ydi. Ijobiy bo'lish mashaqqatli ishni oson va yoqimli qilishga yordam beradi. Amerikaliklar ham juda optimistik (umidli), agar qiziqsangiz, bu maqolada o'qishingiz mumkin.

- O'qitish. Siz o'qituvchi yoki talaba bo'lishingizdan qat'i nazar, o'rganish pozitivlik bilan yaxshilanadi. Agar o'qituvchilar o'z o'quvchilariga g'ayrat va ko'tarinkilikni his qilishlariga yordam berishsa, ular yaxshiroq o'rganadilar. (Aytgancha, ingliz tilini mustaqil o'rganish uchun ham xuddi shunday - bu ijobiy bo'lishga yordam beradi!)

• O'zaro munosabatlarni o'rnatish. Do'stlaringizga, oilangizga, hamkasblaringizga va xo'jayinlaringizga ijobiy narsalarni aytsangiz, ular sizning so'zlaringizni qadrlashadi. Keyin ular siz haqingizda ijobiy fikrlarni o'ylashadi. Har bir inson boshqalar haqida ijobiy narsalarni gapiradigan va o'ylaydigan dunyoni tasavvur qila olasizmi? Bu juda baxtli joy bo'lardi.

Bunga juda ko'p milollar keltirishimiz mumkin:

1. **All the Rage** - juda zamonaviy, olifta

Yoga pants are **all the rage** in North America right now, but in two years probably nobody will be wearing them.

2. **Meeting of the Minds** – juda katta kelishuvga erishmoq

At first the negotiations weren't going well, but when the president of the company and I sat down over drinks, we had a real **meeting of the minds**.

3. **Scare the Living Daylights out of Someone** - Biror kishini qattiq qo'rqitish

I know my boyfriend was just trying to be nice, but when I opened the door to my apartment and everyone yelled "Surprise!" it **scared the living daylights** out of me.

4. **Out of Sight, Out of Mind**- Agar biror narsani yoki kimnidir ko'rmasangiz, u narsa yoki odam haqida unutishga moyil bo'lasiz.

When I broke up with Jake, I was heartbroken. But since he moved away, I hardly ever think about him. **Out of sight, out of mind!**

5. **Tear-Jerker** - Sizni yig'lab yuboradigan film yoki kitob

The film "Love Story," with its story of young love cut short by death, was one of the most successful **tear-jerkers** of all time.

6. **Pet Peeve** - Sizni ayniqsa bezovta qiladigan kichik narsa

My **pet peeve** is people who bring large numbers of items to the express checkout at the supermarket.

7. **Pull Yourself Together** - O'z his-tuyg'ularingizni boshqaring; kuchli hissiy xafagarchilikdan xalos bo'lish

I know it was hard seeing your ex-boyfriend at the bar, but you need to **pull yourself together** so we can go home.

Quydagilar ham ijobiy manodagi frazalogik birliklar: xushomat qilish manosida:

1. **Your skirt is so pretty.** -Sizning yubkangiz juda chiroyli.

Agar sizga kimning kiygan kiyimi yoqsa, ayting!

Your hat is so cute. Where did you get it?

2. **You look great today.** - Bugun ajoyib ko'rinasiz.

Har bir inson o'zini yaxshi ko'rishini bilsa, o'zini yaxshi his qiladi.

You look really cute today!

3. **You're a fantastic cook** - Ushbu tuzilma har qanday odamni maqtash uchun ishlatilishi mumkin.

You're an amazing mother!

4. **I like your new haircut.** - Biror kishida boshqacha narsani sezsangiz, biror narsa aytish yoqimli.

I really like your new belt.

5. **You have the best style** - Ha, tashqi ko'rinish haqida yana bir iltifot!

You have the best voice. I love hearing you sing!

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